

ACTUAL PROBLEMS OF PEDAGOGY IN HIGHER EDUCATION

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Annotation. The article is devoted to the problems of functioning and development of the modern system of higher education. This topic is relevant because the problems of the pedagogical process are complex and significantly affect the development of the country. The article reveals the prospects of overcoming the crisis phenomena in the field of education.

Keywords: information society, pedagogical process, education, innovations, higher education institution, teaching problems, teaching methods, professionalism, labor market, competitiveness, quality of education.

The educational sphere is the most important social institute whose goal is to train and educate versatile personality. Modern conditions informational, political, economic, cultural And other changes provide serious influence on the learning process in higher educational institutions. Based this, purpose modern education can name upbringing personalities, which capable navigate And disclose their capabilities and talents in actively changing conditions.

The future of the nation depends on the quality of education, including the path cultural and scientific development, as well as the situation in the international arena. Based on the importance of this area, questions become relevant Not only modernization education, But and overcoming certain contradictions V system education. Higher education –an important stage in the development of a personality and a specialist in a particular field. The enrichment of scientific potential occurs thanks to higher education. However given sphere slowly adapts To changing conditions.

Studying modern theoretical And applied materials, which dedicated preparation specialists higher educational establishments, demonstrates essential inconsistency educational programs and regulatory documents modern international standards And requirements.

Problematic question is contradiction between level university preparation of an individual with the requirements and expectations of possible employers, which

ultimately leads to a decrease in competitiveness graduates of higher educational institutions. Discrepancy between knowledge and reality conditions of social life makes professional adaptation difficult, leads to long-term crisis formation professional

Can highlight following requirements employers topotential to the employee:

1. Ability on one's own ready working place, to complement official instructions necessary functions V certain conditions;
2. Agreed Job How With primary So And secondary tasks;
3. Skill and pursuit To improvement professionalknowledge and skills, stress resistance etc.

For correct improvement systems necessary clear understanding methods and ways updates systems. For Russian higher education typical absence clear representation O volume, whatway reform pedagogical sphere, What is yourself separate problematic field. Also To problems pedagogy can attributed:

1. Significant lack of funding, cost cutting on education, optimization expenses given spheres. This leads To the decline of pedagogy, as well as the decline in the prestige of the teaching profession. Lack of funds causes a shortage of personnel, specialists in sphere education. Except Togo, V force low salary boards teachers do not have the motivation to present the material in a quality manner. Costs Mark, What financing plays the most important role V technical equipment universities;
2. Ill-conceived mechanism continuity between school, college And university. Basic knowledge, which receives schoolboy, often Not correspond university requirements;
3. Inadequate level of professionalism teachers. How shows practice, often teachers Not have pedagogical education, are selected from numbers students;
4. Absence motivation To quality organizations pedagogical process;

In modern conditions observed a crisis old systems education (higher volume number). Global changes political, economic, economic social areas require compliance systems education advanced standards. Speech coming Not only O methods training, technical equipment educational establishments, But And O roles teacher in the pedagogical process. Currently it is necessarylearn students find useful information, apply her onpractice.

So it is possible do row conclusions:

Education is the most important part of social life. From quality Education depends on the development of the country as a whole. Constantly changing living conditions place high demands on the teaching field and training standards specialists.

There are many problems in pedagogy, including in the field higher education. weighty disadvantage higher education is the discrepancy between the knowledge that students receive and demands of employers, which leads to a crisis of professional formation personality. Except Togo, a lack of financing so same negatively affects education. There is a decrease not only number of teaching staff, but also the quality of teaching process.

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